

Azolla biomass production, Jorhat, India, 1981-82.

Treatments ^a	Azolla biomass (t/ha)												Mean
	1981						1982						
	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	
L ₀ P ₀ I ₁	23.8	6.8	21.0	19.3	14.0	18.5	6.3	18.4	17.5	19.4	21.2	26.5	17.7
L ₀ P ₀ I ₂	28.5	6.7	26.0	22.2	17.4	20.0	8.8	15.0	17.0	18.4	24.0	26.4	19.2
L ₀ P ₁ I ₁	30.3	14.2	27.5	20.8	17.5	25.3	13.5	21.9	25.3	20.2	26.0	29.6	22.7
L ₀ P ₂ I ₁	34.6	14.0	31.0	26.1	23.7	21.3	11.0	21.0	26.4	24.7	22.2	30.3	23.8
L ₀ P ₁ I ₂	29.5	14.7	30.0	25.5	26.6	26.9	15.7	22.5	25.1	20.9	27.1	32.4	24.7
L ₀ P ₂ I ₂	31.9	13.7	32.4	27.7	25.3	30.4	16.3	17.0	19.5	25.0	24.6	34.9	24.9
L ₁ P ₀ I ₁	16.0	4.1	26.0	17.3	12.9	15.4	11.3	12.9	18.6	20.5	23.7	30.8	17.4
L ₁ P ₀ I ₂	28.3	5.6	25.8	20.9	18.0	26.5	18.5	17.0	20.3	19.3	24.4	18.6	20.3
L ₁ P ₁ I ₁	30.0	16.9	31.2	35.2	24.7	28.4	19.2	21.9	20.8	28.1	27.9	35.1	26.6
L ₁ P ₁ I ₂	35.3	12.5	30.4	32.0	27.6	29.2	17.4	25.1	27.2	25.4	29.2	39.3	27.7
L ₁ P ₂ I ₁	31.3	15.9	28.8	30.1	30.1	26.0	19.6	23.0	22.9	24.8	29.9	28.4	25.9
L ₁ P ₂ I ₂	33.7	16.0	33.8	31.0	26.4	30.1	18.4	26.3	26.1	20.5	30.0	34.1	27.2
Mean	29.4	11.7	28.7	25.7	22.0	24.8	14.7	20.2	22.2	22.4	25.8	30.6	
	<i>Mean av water temp (°C)</i>												
	29	38	32	31	26	24	22	25	28	30	30	30	

Season (mo) CD (0.05) 2.768
 Lime (L) 1.151
 Phosphate (P) 1.384
 CV = 14.77%

^a L₀ = no lime, L₁ = 1 t lime/ha, P₀ = no P, P₁ = 9 kg P/ha, P₂ = 18 kg P/ha, I₁ = 0.5 t inoculum/ha, I₂ = 1 t inoculum/ha.

Jul, and was lowest in Aug. Production increased in Sep and then remained stable until Dec (see table). Variations in production were related to weather, particularly temperature. In Aug, when production was lowest, water temperature reached 44° C and averaged 38°C.

Production also varied with nutrient management. Applying 1 t lime and 18 kg P/ha significantly increased production over no-lime and no-P treatments (see table). P affected production more than lime did. Inoculum amount did not affect biomass production. *ℒ*

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Effect of salinity on *Azolla pinnata*

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We studied the effect of salinity on *A. pinnata*, Coimbatore strain, with a soil extract solution with 20 ppm superphosphate as base medium. Sodium chloride was applied at 0.01,

0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09, 0.1, and 0.2%. *A. pinnata* was inoculated at 5 g per plastic container and fresh weight was recorded after 14 d. In another experiment, 500 ppm neem *Azadirachta indica* cake was added to the medium.

A. pinnata yield decreased as salinity increased (see table), but neem cake reduced the detrimental effect of salinity. *ℒ*

Effect of salinity on *A. pinnata*, Tamil Nadu, India.

Sodium chloride (%)	Biomass (g/tub)	% decrease over control	Biomass (g/tub) with neem cake amendment (500 ppm)	% increase or decrease over control
Control without superphosphate	5.3	-	5.4	-
Neem cake alone	NT ^a	-	8.8	+62
0.01	5.2	3	8.5	+57
0.02	5.0	6	7.5	+38
0.03	4.7	11	7.0	+30
0.04	4.7	11	6.7	+24
0.05	4.6	13	5.4	+ 0
0.06	4.4	18	5.2	- 3
0.07	4.3	20	5.2	- 3
0.08	4.0	25	5.2	- 3
0.09	4.0	25	4.8	-11
0.10	3.7	31	4.7	-13
0.20	3.6	32	4.0	-26
SE	0.006		0.577	
CD	0.017		1.678	

^aNot tested.

Rice response to and residual effect of Zn application in a sandy lowland soil

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In 1981 wet season and 1981-82 dry season, we studied IR880 rice response to and residual effect of Zn application in a sandy soil with 1.77 ppm available Zn and pH 7.1. Zn at 0, 2.8, 5.8, 8.5, and 11.5 kg/ha was applied before seeding.

In wet season, plots were in a randomized complete block design with eight replications. To study residual effect in dry season, Zn was applied to four of the same plots and the remaining four received no Zn.

In wet season, all treatments were significantly better than no-Zn control. Rice yield increased from 3.4 to 4.5 t/ha (see figure). In dry season, rice yield increased from 3.5 to 5.0 t/ha (see figure), and best results were obtained with 8.5 and 11.5 kg Zn/ha.

Zn application had a substantial residual effect (see table). Although